

Paraphrase of the concept philosophy and theory

Philosophy and theory are the antonym of hallucination and delusion. In other words, science is a chain which consists of two parts and these parts can be health opposite to sick. Hallucination and delusion are sick (UvA). The difference between the two parts of the chain is that one of them is autotroph and the other is heterotroph. Autotroph and heterotroph are concepts from biology which describe the two parts of a food chain where the heterotroph needs an autotroph, which produces food one's self (fig.1) (Börger and Broekhuizen). The set philosophy and hallucination is autotroph. The set theory and delusion is heterotroph. Sans Science states in a comic that philosophy differs from theoretical physics/mathematics (fig.2) (JU Physics Memes). Doctor Esquirol states the concept hallucination for the first time in 1817 (Wikipedia). "(H)alucinari" is a Latin word which means speaking nonsense (Van Dale). "De alieno corie ludere" is a Latin saying which means playing around another skin d.i. possession (Montijn). "Allochtoon" is a Dutch word based on Greek words "allos" which means another and "chthon" which means ground or land (Van Dale). "Autochtoon" is a Dutch word based on Greek words "autos" which means self and "chthon" which means ground or land (Van Dale). Paraphrasing the concept hallucination and delusion is autotroph - and heterotroph hallucination. Paraphrasing the concept philosophy and theory is autotroph - and heterotroph autucination. Autucination is a neo-logism.

Paraphrasing is relevant, because it could contribute to a better therapeutical relationship. Furthermore, it could trigger research about the science chain's anatomy and it's cure. There are pink pills which mark where one didn't clean one's teeth (fig. 3) (Wikipedia). It would be handy to mark where one's science chain is sick, for example to diagnose if treatment is necessary or successful. There aren't empty (locked) psychiatric wards/prisons yet (SOS, UvA).

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

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